

Application and Development of Ho Chi Minh Thoughts on Mass Mobilization Affairs in the Party Congress XIII Documents

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Abstract: Thoroughly imbedded and creatively applied Marx-Leninism on people's role and inherited the tradition on mobilization of people's strength in the country's sovereignty protection and defence, President Ho Chi Minh always stressed the strategic importance and decisiveness of mass mobilization affairs in the revolution process. It is therefore important to understand the creative application and development of the Ho Chi Minh thoughts in the Party Congress XIII documents. This paper clarifies Ho Chi Minh thoughts on mobilization affairs and its application in the Party Congress XIII document.

Key words: Ho Chi Minh thoughts, mass mobilization affairs, people's mobilization, the Party's National Congress XIII

1. Ho Chi Minh Thoughts on Mass Mobilization Affairs

Throughout the history, Vietnam encountered and defeated many foreign invaders thanks to the nation's patriotism, unitedness, resilience and indomitability. These are root causes for our strength to defeat giant invaders. The national history, practical lessons learnt in the Vietnamese context and the deep understanding of Marx-Leninism shaped the Ho Chi Minh's ideology, ethical standards and approach on mass mobilization affairs, which is not only an invaluable heritage but also an important success factor of Vietnam's revolution.

Ho Chi Minh's thoughts on mass mobilization affairs are concepts, direction, and content on mass mobilization affairs imbedded and reflected in his speeches and actions. The love of people and human beings, great trust in people's unitedness, people's dedication and service orientedness are core elements of his thoughts on mass mobilization affairs.

People's role and strength

President Ho Chi Minh always valued people's position, role and strength: "people are the most valuable and most important", are "supreme", "there is nothing out there more valuable than the people. Nothing is stronger than people's united forces"¹; people's strength is invincible: "Easy tasks may fail without people's support, difficult tasks may be fulfilled with people's will"². He indicated clearly that: "Our own experience and in other countries proved that any difficulty or challenge may be overcome with people's great support. It would be difficult otherwise"³. He confirmed: Revolution is the people's cause, not of any individual hero". People are the root of the country and the key forces of revolution. The country needs to ground on people to be viable. "Strong root sustains the tree, strong people build success". With the Party "nothing gets done without people's support"⁴. He considers the revolution is people's cause while people needs Party to show the way. The Party has responsibility to unite, mobilize and lead people to revolutionize. Ho Chi Minh's science-based great idea is: Revolution is the people's cause. Key issue of all revolutions is the union of people and mass mobilization. Party is a part of people, no matter how great it is. He raised a theory that proven to be the truth: "The mass mobilization affairs is so important that it induces other works. Good mass mobilization makes other work go smoothly while the bad mass mobilization hinders everything"⁵. Therefore, it is important to understand that mass mobilization is the revolution's decisive success factor. There are four important key tasks as follows:

First, keeping people informed of their rights, Party's directions, decisions and state's policies that affect people's life.

Second, explaining clearly for the people. "First and foremost it is important to explain for everyone that it is for their benefit and their responsibility. As such, they need to commit their best for accomplishment of the the tasks. Mass mobilization

¹ Ho Chi Minh: All works collection, volume 8, National Political Publishing House, Ha Noi, 2000, p.276.

² Ho Chi Minh: All works collection, National Political Publishing House, Ha Noi, 2002, volume 12, p.212.

³ Ho Chi Minh: All works collection, volume 5, National Political Publishing House, H, 2011, p.335.

⁴ Ho Chi Minh: All works collection, volume 5, National Political Publishing House, H, 2011, p.278.

⁵ Ho Chi Minh: All works collection, National Political Publishing House, Ha Noi 2011, volume 6, p.234

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includes not only “posters, books, meetings, slogans, leaflets, instructions”⁶ but also communication and explanation for people’s understanding reasons for a revolution. President Ho Chi Minh indicated that “...revolution is raising people’s awareness”⁷, meaning that communication and explanation for people’s understanding.

Third, showing people ways. It means that anything should be discussed, consulted for their inputs and experience, plan together with people in line with local context, encourage and mobilize all people to carry out. It is necessary to monitor, support, and encourage people throughout the implementation process.

Fourth, reviewing, drawing experience and lessons learnt. “After implementation, it is important to review the process with the people, draw experience, criticize and praise accordingly”⁸.

In addition, clearly identifying the responsible people for mass mobilization affairs: “all cadres of government agencies, mass organizations or members of people’s entities (Lien Viet, Viet Minh...) should be in charge of mass mobilization affairs”. This is not only the responsibility of the mass mobilization affairs professional staff but of all forces in the political system, primarily the government agencies. It implies that all cadres in the government should be responsible for mass mobilization affairs. This is a typical characteristic of mass mobilization affairs when the Party-state is in place. The government is people’s main instrument. The government therefore has not only carry the mass mobilization but also sufficient conditions to do it more effectively.

With people-based approach, Ho Chi Minh requests the Party, government as well as all cadres and members to serve and learn from people “Our regime is democracy, meaning the people are the owner. As the ruling Party, all cadres, from central to regional, provincial, district, commune and local levels, should be a loyal servant of the people.”⁹

Another approach that reflects the depth and width of the people-based principle is to trust people, respect people, understand people, dialogue with people, set example before the people and take criticism from people. Ho Chi Minh points out the solution for fixing bureaucracy, being distant from people is a six-element principle as follows: (i) putting people’s interests above everything; (ii) contacting closely with people; (iii) discussion and explanation for people to understand clearly; (iv) self criticizing and taking criticisms if commit mistakes; (v) being willing to learn from people; (vi) setting good examples of being hard working, economical, clean and ethical for people to follow.¹⁰ The mass mobilization can only unlock people’s strength if carried out properly. Ho Chi Minh stressed: “All the Party’s direction, decisions and policies should be aiming at improving people’s life”¹¹. He also set an ideological foundation for “people know, people discuss, people take actions and people check” principle, which has been always undertaken by the Party.

The Ho Chi Minh’s thoughts on mass mobilization is an invaluable asset. This is heritage of our ancestor’s tradition on people-based, people’s trust and people’s respect, the cultural, humane values with the Marx Leninism at the peak.

2. Application and development of Ho Chi Minh’s thoughts on the mass mobilization affairs of Communist Party of Vietnam

The Communist Party of Vietnam inherits and develops ideologies of Karl Marx, Frederik Engels, V.I. Lenin and Ho Chi Minh on people’s role and the importance of of Party-people relation and the mass mobilization affairs. The Party confirms: “The Party is the leader, while the revolution is the people’s cause. In the reform period, the Party takes the very first lesson learnt is “people-based” approach. The Party Congress X also confirmed: “People’s trust, support and assistance is the root strength, price of all victories and invaluable asset of the Party”.¹²

The Party Congress XIII continues this spirit with the following tasks and measures:

First, making radical changes in awareness and action of the Party’s committees and political system on mass mobilization affairs in the new context

The underlying reason that the Congress XIII set the priority task “To make radical changes in awareness and action of the Party’s committees and political system on mass mobilization affairs”¹³ is that the new context requires radical changes and strong actions with higher responsibility of the Party cadres and government officials to fulfill mass mobilization targets. Moreover, the awareness on mass mobilization remains limited without adequate responsibility and cooperation effectiveness, lack of attention to people’s mobilization and persuasion to reach consensus. Therefore it is necessary to communicate and educate to raise awareness of society, primarily the Party’s committees and mass organizations, on promotion of people’s important role in defending and

⁶ Ho Chi Minh: All works collection, volume 6, National Political Publishing House, H, 2011, p.232.

⁷ Ho Chi Minh: All works collection, volume 2, National Political Publishing House, H, 2011, p.288.

⁸ Ho Chi Minh: All works collection, volume 6, National Political Publishing House, H, 2011, p.233.

⁹ Ho Chi Minh: All works collection, volume 13, National Political Publishing House, H, 2011, p.83-84.

¹⁰ Ho Chi Minh: All works collection, volume 7, National Political Publishing House, H, 2011, p.177

¹¹ Ho Chi Minh: All works collection, volume 13, National Political Publishing House, H, 2011, p.164.

¹² Communist Party of Vietnam, *National Congress X document*, National Political Publishing House, Ha Noi, 2006, p.304.

¹³ Communist Party of Vietnam, *National Congress XIII document*, volume 2, National Political Publishing House, Ha Noi, 2021, p.248.

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development the country, socialist democracy and implementation of mass mobilization affairs in accordance to “the regulations on mass mobilization of political system” issued by Politbureau tenure X. Strengthen the people’ trust on the Party and State, all nation unity and close relationship between the Party and the people.

In order to raise awareness, responsibility of the Party’s committees and political system on mass mobilization affairs, it is important to focus on the following issues:

organizing effectively the implementation of the Party’s directions and decisions and state policies and laws on mass mobilization affairs, discussion of mass mobilization affairs in the monthly Party’s cells meetings.

Second, development of a team of cadres that “truly respect people, trust people, understand people, interactive with people, willing to learn from people and responsible before the people”. Training, education and development of professional team of cadres on mass mobilization affairs.

The underlying reason the Congress XIII document set out the solution “development of a team of cadres that “truly respect people, trust people, understand people, be close with people, willing to learn from people and responsible before the people”¹⁴ and “listen to people, make people understand, convince people” is that respecting people makes cadres close leaders and servants of people, who approach people as their owners and teachers. “being interactive with people” is a requirement for mass mobilization cadre. Those who are close to people are unlikely to be bureaucratic, arrogant, dictative: “trusting people, understanding people” helps cadres fully put themselves in the people’ shoes and make relevant policy recommendations for the Party’s committees and government to issue. In order to “learn from people”, the cadres need to be modest, open and attentive. People are smart and experienced in various aspects for cadres to learn. Thus the cadres need to strive to work for people’ happiness and interests and avoid harming people in any way as Ho Chi Minh instructed.

On the other hand, it is necessary to train the mass mobilization cadres in the mass movement, to gain people’ confidence and trust. Because people who have been through the practical experience will easily gain people’ trust, confidence and love. These are keys to convince people - “skillfull mass mobilization”, which is a success factor in any work.

The mass mobilization cadres should set good examples. Ho Chi Minh asked the cadres to join people in the works and criticized the “lip service”, actions do not follow the words, lack of field experience, limited interaction with people. He stressed the need to: “pay attention and invest on training, education and development of professional mass mobilization cadres”¹⁵.

It is critical to: (i) train and develop capable team of mass mobilization cadres professionally, practically and politically, which fulfill requirements of mass mobilization affairs in the new context. It is necessary to enable the mass mobilization cadres to study and obtain new knowledge, develop adequate policies and incentives for cadres to enhance their knowledge, self-study, self learning through daily activities. (ii) develop policies and mechanisms for talented, capable and experienced people attraction, development and retainment; rotation, training, appointment, promotion of mass mobilization cadres, particularly the young ones: prevent assigning incapable cadres to carry out mass mobilization affairs.

In addition, pay adequate attention in development of mass mobilization cadres among reputation people in ethnic minorities, religious groups. These are extended arms of the Party and government to the people.

Third, renewing and enhancing the effectiveness of mass mobilization affairs by the Party, government and local authorities

Over the past time, the effectiveness of resolutions, mass mobilization programmes, development of working regulations remains limited. Renewing the issuance of mass mobilization resolutions, programmes is important. The institutionalization of related resolutions and programmes is slow. The forecast, assessment of situations and events is not effective. The understanding of non-state workers, intellectuals, religious groups’ thinking and concerns is unsatisfactory. A number of hot spots in Binh Duong, Dong Nai, Van Giang, Tien Lang, Muong Nhe, Dong Tam...show ineffectiveness of forecast, cooperation, handling situation...

The effects and effectiveness of state management and policy and legal enforcement remains limited, particularly in land management, environment, investment, urban development, labour relations...Interest groups, bribes, corruption make people, businesses unhappy. The weakly implemented grassroots democracy, particularly the consultation on implementation of socio-economic development projects induces lengthy complaints, legal cases in a number of places.

¹⁴ Communist Party of Vietnam, *National Congress XIII document*, volume 2, National Political Publishing House, Ha Noi, 2021, p.248.

¹⁵ Communist Party of Vietnam, *National Congress XIII document*, volume 2, National Political Publishing House, Ha Noi, 2021, p.249.

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The Congress XIII outlines: “Continue to renew and enhance the effectiveness of mass mobilization affairs of Party, state and government agencies at various levels”¹⁶. These include the issuance of resolutions, agendas of mass mobilization to ensure Party’s leadership and resolve pressing issues and conflicts, address properly the people’s concerns and recommendations.

Fourth, strengthening social monitoring and debate, consultation with Fatherland Front, mass organizations and people; diversifying the mass mobilization formats and methods to understand and address people’s needs and wishes in timely manner

The reason Congress XIII resolution set out the solution “Strengthening quality of social monitoring and debate, consultation of Fatherland Front and mass organizations”¹⁷ is that the role of Fatherland Front and mass organizations in social monitoring and debate, consultation on Party and government building and state management remains limited.

In order to strengthen the quality of social monitoring and debate, the Party’s committees should respect the independence, accountability of Fatherland Front and mass organizations while enable these organizations to be more active in their operation to become more interactive and responsive to people.

Fifth, actively checking, supervising and inspecting the implementation of Party’s resolutions on mass mobilization affairs

The Congress XIII document suggests: “actively checking, supervising and inspecting the implementation of Party’s resolutions on mass mobilization affairs”¹⁸ because the monitoring, supervision on implementation of the Party’s documents on mass mobilization has not been conducted regularly. There has been limited consultation with people upon issuance of policies; meeting, dialoguing and resolution of complaints remains limited...

Therefore, the Party organizations from central to local level should renew their leadership, checking, supervising, inspection of the implementation of the Party’s resolutions and directions on mass mobilization affairs. Strengthen the inspection, checking the public service implementation, penalizing violations, corruptions and wrong-doings, removing corrupted and incapable cadres and officials.

In addition, it is important to resolve the complex and long pending cases, which are socially and politically potential disorder through meeting, dialoguing with people, working out the implementation roadmap and resolving the conflicts at local level.

¹⁶ Communist Party of Vietnam, *National Congress XIII document*, volume 2, National Political Publishing House, Ha Noi, 2021, p.248.

¹⁷ Communist Party of Vietnam, *National Congress XIII document*, volume 2, National Political Publishing House, Ha Noi, 2021, p.249.

¹⁸ Communist Party of Vietnam, *National Congress XIII document*, volume 2, National Political Publishing House, Ha Noi, 2021, p.249.